

SHORT COMMUNICATION

New Quinolone Alkaloids from *Ravenia spectabilis* Engl

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In a previous communication¹ the isolation of γ -fagarine and arborinine from the leaves of *Ravenia spectabilis* (family *Rutaceae*) was described. We now report on two new quinolone alkaloids, ravenine (I) and ravenoline (III) and a third alkaloid later identified as atanine² (IV) obtained from the same source.

Ravenine, m.p. 120-21°, ravenoline, m.p. 144°; (α)_D+6° (CHCl₃) and atanine, m. p. 134°, were assigned the same molecular formula C₁₅H₁₇NO₂ (M⁺243). The UV absorption spectra showed maxima at 224 (log ϵ 4.69), 228 (log ϵ 4.72), 268 (log ϵ 3.85), 278 (log ϵ 3.80), 316 (log ϵ 3.79) and 330 m μ (log ϵ 3.67) for ravenine; 229 (log ϵ 4.51), 242 sh (log ϵ 4.06), 275 (log ϵ 3.67), 286 (log ϵ 3.70), 320 (log ϵ 3.81) and 334 m μ (log ϵ 3.63) for ravenoline and 224 (log ϵ 4.57), 228 (log ϵ 4.56), 270 (log ϵ 3.77), 278 (log ϵ 3.82), 311 (log ϵ 3.76), 321 (log ϵ 3.90) and 338 m μ (log ϵ 3.71) for the third alkaloid (atanine). Their IR spectra have a band at 1645 cm⁻¹ (cyclic amide). This spectral behaviour^{3,4} is suggestive of a 2-quinolone skeleton.

(I) R = -CH₂CH=CMe₂

(II) R = H

(III)

(IV)

(V)

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The NMR spectrum of ravenine showed two singlets at δ 1.76 and 1.82 ppm for two gem-methyl groups, a three-proton singlet at δ 3.65 ppm ($>N-\underline{CH}_3$), a two-proton doublet at δ 4.64 ppm ($-CH_2-CH=$), an one-proton multiplet at δ 5.53 ppm ($-CH_2-CH=$), an one-proton singlet at δ 6.07 ppm (H^3) and four aromatic protons at δ 7.18-8.1 ppm. The important peaks in mass fragmentation spectrum of ravenine are at 228 (M-15), 175 (M-68), 105 and 77. The compound on treatment with hydrobromic acid in acetic acid, furnished a phenol (II), m.p. 272°, which was identified as N-methyl-4-hydroxy-2-quinolone.

The above data lead to the formulation of ravenine as (I), which has been recently synthesised by Chamberlain and Grundon⁵.

The NMR spectrum of ravenoline showed a three-proton doublet at δ 1.39 ppm ($J=7$ c/s, $-\underline{CH}-\underline{CH}_3$), a three-proton weakly splitted signal at δ 1.82 ppm ($J=1$ c/s, $=\underline{C}-\underline{CH}_3$), a three-proton singlet at δ 3.71 ppm ($>N-\underline{CH}_3$), an one-proton multiplet at δ 4.20 ppm ($>CH-CH_3$) a two-proton multiplet at δ 5.28 ppm ($>C=CH_2$), a one-proton singlet at δ 7.30 ppm ($-OH$) and four aromatic protons at δ 7.18-8.1 ppm. In mass fragmentation spectrum the major peaks are at 228 (M-15), 214 (M-29), 200, 188, 134 and 77. The above data, alkali solubility and abnormal Claisen rearrangement⁶ of ravenine to ravenoline lead to the formulation of the latter as (III).

The third alkaloid had the NMR values identical with those of atanine. The compound on treatment with hydrobromic acid in acetic acid furnished dihydrofindersine(V).

Details of the work will be published later on.

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